

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ВЗАИМОСВЯЗЬ МЕЖДУ КОГНИТИВНЫМ СТИЛЕМ ПОЛЕНЕЗАВИСИМОСТЬ-ПОЛЕЗАВИСИМОСТЬ И ОПЫТОМ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ СЕТЬЮ ИНСТАГРАМ

Савина Я.М.

*Научный руководитель
Университет КАЗГЮУ имени М. Нарикбаева*

Боранишинова Д.

*Бакалавр Социальных наук: Психология
Университет КАЗГЮУ имени М. Нарикбаева*

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN COGNITIVE STYLE FIELD-INDEPENDENCE-FIELD-DEPENDENCE WITH SOCIAL NETWORK EXPERIENCE ON INSTAGRAM

Savina Ya.

*Supervisor
M. Narikbayev KAZGUU University*

Boranshinova D.

*Bachelor of Science in Psychology
M. Narikbayev KAZGUU University
School of Liberal Arts*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Предыстория: исследование основано на теории когнитивного стиля полнезависимость-полезависимость, где первый предполагает автономию в большей степени и ориентацию, направленную на себя, а второй — меньшую автономию и межличностную ориентацию. В данной статье работе полнезависимость-полезависимость рассматривается как широкий поведенческий стиль, определяющий опыт человека в социальной сети Instagram, где массовые стандарты и предубеждения о красоте, успехе, а также давление обратной связи может повлиять на благополучие пользователя с двусмысленными обстоятельствами.

Цель: изучить, коррелирует ли когнитивный стиль полнезависимость-полезависимость с положительным и отрицательным опытом в Инстаграм среди молодых людей в Казахстане.

Дизайн: Количественный не экспериментальный дизайн исследования.

Выборка: Метод детерминированной и удобной выборки. В исследовании приняли участие 44 молодых человека в возрасте от 18 до 24 лет, из них 4 парней и 40 девушек.

Меры: Тест Включенных фигур с 30 сложными фигурами для измерения когнитивного стиля полнезависимость и полезависимость, а также опрос с 27 элементами (7 общих) для исследования практики использования сети Инстаграм.

Статистический анализ критерий хи-квадрат с критическими значениями 5,1 ($df2$), 7,8 ($df3$), 9,5 ($df4$) и p -значением 0,05.

Результаты: 7 пунктов опроса продемонстрировали значительную взаимосвязь между когнитивным стилем полнезависимость-полезависимость и опытом использования социальной сети Инстаграм, в то время как 13 компонентов не подтвердили взаимосвязь.

Ограничения: маленький размер выборки с низкой репрезентативностью; один статистический инструмент для статистического анализа.

Вывод: результаты являются предварительными в попытке продемонстрировать целостный характер человеческого функционирования, включая как познание, так и личность, и его роль в социальной сети Инстаграм.

ABSTRACT

Background: The study is based on the theoretical framework of Cognitive style Field-Independence and Field-Dependence, where first one implies greater autonomy and impersonal orientation, while the latter one less autonomy and interpersonal orientation. In this paper field-independence-field-dependence is considered as a broad behavioral style determining performance of an individual within the Social Network Instagram experience, where mass standards and biases of beauty, success as well as feedback pressure can influence a user's well-being with equivocal circumstances.

Aim: To explore whether cognitive style Field-Independence-Field-Dependence correlates with positive and negative Instagram experience among young adults in Kazakhstan.

Design: Quantitative non-experimental research design.

Sample: Non-probability convenience sampling technique. 44 young adults between 18 to 24 years of age, where 4 males and 40 females participated in the study.

Measures: Embedded Figure Test with 30 items to measure cognitive style field-independence-field-dependence and self-administered survey with 27 items (7 general) to observe Social Network Instagram experience.

Statistical analysis: Chi-square test with critical values of 5,1 (df_2), 7,8 (df_3), 9,5 (df_4) and p -value of 0,05.

Results: 7 items of a survey illustrated a significant relationship between cognitive style field-independence-field-dependence and Social Network Instagram experience, while 13 components did not support the relationship.

Limitations: Small sample size with low representativeness; one statistical tool to make statistical analysis.

Conclusion: The results are provisional in an attempt to demonstrate the holistic nature of human functioning including both cognition and personality and its role on Social Media Instagram.

Ключевые слова: когнитивный стиль, полнезависимость, полезависимость, перцепция, поведение, автономность, обработка информации, ментальные модели, социальная сеть Инстаграм, стандарты красоты, пищевое поведение, сравнение, негативный опыт, позитивный опыт, хи-квадрат, корреляционный анализ.

Keywords: cognitive style, field-independence, field-dependence, perception, behavior, autonomy, processing of information, mental models, social media Instagram, standards of beauty, eating behavior, comparison, negative experience, positive experience, chi-square, correlational analysis.

Cognitive style is an individual's preferred way of gathering, processing, and evaluating information. It impacts how people scan their environment for information, how they organize and interpret, and how they integrate collected data into the subjective theories and mental model that navigate their actions.¹⁶

Field-independence - cognitive styles; general ability to overcome embedding contexts in perception.¹⁷

Field-dependence

Cognitive restructuring skills a technique aims to identify and restructure false beliefs or biases, so that they are adaptive and reasonable.¹⁸

Mental model how we understand the world. The model guides the way we think and how we understand, also they shape the connections and opportunities that we see.¹⁹

Autonomy independence from frame and external referents. Self-government and responsible control for one's life.²⁰

Social Media internet-based channels that allow users to advantageously interact and selectively manage online identity, either in real-time or clocklessly. with both broad and narrow audiences who derive value from user-generated content and perceived interactivity with others.²¹

Contingencies of self-worth are the domains in which people invest their self-esteem. Thus, progress or success in these domains boosts state self-esteem, and failures or setbacks lead to drops in state self-esteem.²²

Collectivism one of the types of social organization in which the individual is seen as being subordinate to a social collectivity such as a nation, a state, a race, or a social class.²³

Interaction an occasion when two or more people or things communicate with or react to each other.²⁴

Cognition the mechanisms that enable the gathering, processing, keeping and use of information, which include perception, memory, learning, and decision making.²⁵

Referent the idea, thing or person that a phrase, word, or object refers to.²⁶

Chapter one: Introduction and background information

1.1 Introduction

This paragraph aims to demonstrate the research topic of the study, focusing on the relationship between cognitive style Field-Independence-Field-Dependence and Social Media Instagram usage experience in the framework of Cognitive Psychology. This part includes the background, research problem, research questions, hypothesis, purpose of the study and its significance.

*For the sake of brevity, cognitive style, field-dependence and field-independence will be called hereafter as CS, FI and FD.

1.2 Background information

Human is a whole organism with interwoven cognition allowing one to think, feel, perceive and behave (Kolb, 1984, p. 31). In the middle of the twentieth century the term cognitive style emerged as a reflection of holistic human functioning. Particularly, cognitive style defines perception, analysis, structure and categorization of information (Gardner, Holzman, Klein, Lipton, Spence, 1959; Kagan, 1966; Witkin, Oltman, Raskin, Karp, 1971; and etc.). In addition, these individual differences in perception were also associated with personality tendencies (Witkin, 1954). At the same time, Klein and Schlesinger (1951), considered CS as a pattern to adaptation to the external world that regulates an individual's cognitive functioning. Thus, as cognitive style defines all psychological processes, it proposes a simple and interesting definition: style is a person (Georges-Louis Leclerc de Buffon, eighteenth century). One of the styles that Witkin (1954) came up with is Field-Independence and Field-Dependence, where the former one exhibited low dependency on the field, while the latter one-high dependency on the surrounding field. FI individuals have greater individual autonomy and disembedding ability. Autonomy, in fact, is one of the factors of psychological well-being

¹⁶ Hayes, J., & Allinson, C. W. (1998)

¹⁷ Witkin, H. A., & Goodenough, D. R. (1977).

¹⁸ Concordia University. (2020, March 4).

¹⁹ Jones, N. A., H. Ross, T. Lynam, P. Perez, and A. Leitch. 2011.

²⁰ Fotiadis, A., Abdulrahman, K., & Spyridou, A. (2019).

²¹ Carr, C. T., & Hayes, R. A. (2015).

²² Crocker, J., & Wolfe, C. T. (2001).

²³ Collectivism | sociology. (2022). Encyclopedia Britannica.

²⁴ Cambridge Dictionary. (2022a, May 25).

²⁵ Witkin, H. A., & Goodenough, D. R. (1977).

²⁶ Cambridge Dictionary. (2022, May 25).

according to Self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 2008). Hence, it is possible to consider, cognitive style FI-FD can give an in-depth explanation to the nature of personality regarding autonomy characteristics. According to M. Kozhevnikov (2007) cognitive styles have a predictive power better than intelligence and situational factors. In fact, in the field of organizational psychology, cognitive style is a fundamental factor determining both individual and organizational behavior (Hayes & Allinson, 1994). Similarly, it has predictive power in academic achievement (Sternberg & Zhang, 2001). Therefore, this pattern can be investigated in other field, such as Social media Instagram. Indeed, according to NapoleonCat (2022) approximately 1, 476 000 000 million people use Instagram each month worldwide. In particular, Kazakhstan's population constituted 12 463 200 users in March 2022, which accounted for 64.9% of its entire population. This percentage shows how big the scope is and how significant the impact on people lives can be. Moreover, social media is a place distinctive from reality. Specifically, it gives more freedom and control at managing online identity and lifestyle with the use of photoshop and filters. In addition, asynchrony of Instagram interaction "allow greater self-presentation by providing individuals time to selectively and opportunistically construct and present themselves online" (Walther, 1995, 1996). As a result, this "made-up" content can distort percep-

tion of self and the world in general. Moreover, the effect is exacerbated as Instagram connects with mass audiences who share two-way interaction and feedback (likes, comments, reactions) as it runs the risk of dependence in users and emotional responses (Marwick & Boyd, 2011; Kent, 2010). Consequently, more people, especially young adults may experience poor psychological well-being if their condition is contingent on the feedback and if they depend on external referents as standards. It is significant to summarize that, Instagram has already woven itself into the tapestry of our daily life and, therefore, disembedding ability of FI cognitive style can come in handy when disembedding the outward feedback and standards of beauty, lifestyle and success.

1.3 Problem statement

In nature, Kazakhstan is a collectivistic country, giving priority to social collections as a referent. This tendency can be also applied to Social Network experience on Instagram with equivocal consequences. It can be investigated through the prism of FI-FD, where the former one implies reliance on self and greater autonomy, while the latter one means reliance on external referents and less autonomy. Thus, we can understand whether cognitive style plays predictive power in Social Network Instagram experience, causing unhealthy comparison, undervalue of achievement, dependence on feedback, etc.

Figure 1. The illustration of Instagram influence on FI-FD

1.4 Purpose of the study

The present correlational study has a purpose to explore whether cognitive style Field-Independence-Field-Dependence correlates with positive and negative Instagram experience among young adults in Kazakhstan.

Objectives:

Conduct a comprehensive analysis with:

- Embedded Figure Test

- Survey
- Combined Interview

1.5 Research Questions

This quantitative study is navigated by the following research question and sub-questions:

The overarching research question is:

1. Does cognitive style FI-FD have the predictive power at Social Network experience on Instagram?

Subsidiary questions include:

1.1 To what extent Field-Independent and Field-Dependent individuals disembed Instagram content of success and beauty from perception of self and one's lifestyle?

1.2 To what extent Field-Independent and Field-Dependent individuals base their feeling of self-esteem and self-worth on feedback that they receive-or fail to receive (likes, comments, reactions etc.)

Hypothesis:

H0: There is no relationship between Field-Independent-Field-Dependent cognitive style and Social Network experience on Instagram.

H0: There is no relationship between Field-Independent individuals and positive Social Network experience on Instagram.

There is no relationship between Field-Dependent Individuals and negative Social Network experience on Instagram.

Ha: There is a relationship between Field-Independent-Field-Dependent cognitive style and Social Network experience on Instagram.

Ha: There is a relationship between Field-Independent and positive Social Network experience on Instagram.

Ha: There is a relationship between Field-Dependent and negative Social Network experience on Instagram.

1.6 Significance and contribution of the study

The study is conducted on the relationship between CS FI-FD and Social Network Experience on Instagram.

The findings can possibly contribute to several audiences. Firstly, young people, especially students will comprehend the importance of referent on which they rely, whether it is inward characterizing FI individuals or outward referring to FD ones. Thus, this perspective can guide them through experience on any Social Media, where comparison, unhealthy standards, hate and

any kind of pressure can take place corrupting the mental health of young users.

Secondly, parents will possibly take into consideration the manner of upbringing. Specifically, educating children to be autonomous when making decisions, solving problems and sharing opinions independent of others "mark". Thirdly, authorities in the educational field will probably implement some changes within teaching techniques knowing the difference between FI and FD students, where later ones stand in need of additional attention and support.

Chapter two: Literature review

2.1 Personality through perception

Human is a holistic entity, where individual differences in cognition related to personality, social relationship and adaptation to the world (Witkin, 1977, p. 15, Kolb, 1974). Specifically, it is in the CS, the way intelligence is directed, a person's preferred way of scanning their environment for information, organizing and interpreting this information, and how they integrate their interpretations into mental models and subjective theories that guide their actions (Hayes and Allinson, 1994). Hence, Hayes and Allinson (1994) considered CS as a pervasive personality variable. This definition is also supported by two opposite approaches: the phenomenological approach of Gregorc led him and Ward (1977) that style characteristics are related to the whole system of thought and that "these characteristics are integrally tied to deep psychological constructs", while experiential learning of Kolb viewing CS as adaptation to the world requiring a whole-perception, cognition, thinking, feeling and behaving (J. Dewey, K. Lewin, J. Piaget; Gregorc, 1982, p. 51; Kolb, 1984, p. 31). Consequently, the prior findings have illustrated the integrated nature of CS: how cognition is directly related to personality and how the latter one from social connection and see the world.

Figure 2. The illustration of interaction between human and world via cognition

In nature, CS have 2 dimensions and each of them is necessary. The word style emerges from the greek word "stylos" meaning a ward which served to write on a wax board. One end was aimed to write, the other to erase. Hence, the value can only be judged with reference to their adaptiveness in particular life circumstances (Messick, 2004). One of the style which will be discussed in this thesis is Field-Independence and

Field-dependence based on Herman Witkin's theory, 1977.

2.2 Field-Independence and Field-Dependence

What is known about cognitive style field independence-field-dependence is largely based on Herman "Hy" Witkin's work. Generally, he stated that differentiation construct, emanating from psychological differentiation theory (1962), is a major formal property of an organismic system. That is the variety of activities,

functions, the level of segregation between the inner and the outer constitute the more or less differentiated world. This broad construct was manifested in a series of Witkin's studies (1941) which were based on a unifying theoretical framework- individual differences in FD. These explorations included cross-cultural study of Pygmy and Bantu people, study on sex chromosome anomalies, study on teaching and learning styles in the classroom, study on doctor-patient relationship in psychotherapy and factor analytic study of individual differences in perceptual-cognitive functioning. The last is the primary focus of this paper. Some preliminary work was carried out in the early 1948 till 1962 where the way to understand the perception of the upright had been modifying as new studies were conducted. In the beginning, Witkin and Asch (1948) conducted a Rod-and-Frame test observing perception of the upright. The experiment involved a tilted square frame with a rod in the middle in an otherwise dark room, where subjects faced a conflict between visual-the rod and body cues. The former cue was intended to help subjects adjust the rod to the vertical position (Wapner,). Here, the individual differences in cognitive-perceptual functioning came into play. Specifically, FD individuals relied primarily on visual cues and less on body ones, while FI vice versa. This pattern, in fact, was observed across many tests of orientation perception (Witkin et al., 1954). Thus, the term FD described effects of the tilted visual field. This method is in line with the Embedded Figure test, where subjects had to find a simple figure from the complex pattern. In this experiment, FD had less disembedding ability in comparison with FI. The correlation between two experiments made Witkin and other scientists (1954) to modify conflict theory into cognitive capacity to disembed the rod from the frame. Last modification redefined the FD as the capacity to overcome, or analyze, an embedding context in perceptual functioning (Witkin et al., 1962). Considering the number of tests and subsequent number of studies on FD construct-Witkin's assumptions seem to be well-grounded.

The perceptual and personality differences between FI and FD individuals is better illustrated through the prism of self non-self segregation as one of the manifestations of the psychological differentiation theory (Witkin, 1962). This proposition implies the awareness of a distinction between one's own and others' characteristics, desires and emotions. The preliminary studies conducted by Witkin and Goodenough (1977) found that FD individuals have less self non-self segregation and are prone to rely on external referents. In turn, it explains their interpersonal orientation. Thus, they tend to be open emotionally and be close physically in social connections. However, FD subjects have less autonomy and lower cognitive restructuring ability, acceding to field's dominant properties and exhibiting high dependency on the field. In contrast, FI are more autonomous, relying on self and have greater restructuring ability, changing the field on their own, showing low dependency on the field. Contrary to FD, FI are impersonal illustrating emotional and physical distance.

But, it is significant to mention that both styles are equally valued. Cognitive style is an identifying manner of how individual communicate with the world, thus it is different for everyone. Therefore, Witkin and Goodenough draw our attention to non-evaluative (good or bad) perspective, but rather look at both FI/FD as adaptive in a particular context.

2.3 Predictive power of Field-Independence-Field-Dependence

Throughout 50 years from 1965 cognitive style FI-FD have been investigating one the nature of predictive power. In fact, there is a considerable amount of studies proving this argument to be right in the perspective of a broad behavioral style, while others found no reason to define FI-FD in this manner, but rather as a perceptual/visual/ spatial ability. Before diving into the analysis of findings, it is important to mention that FI-FD was measured by EFT/RFT in all consecutive studies.

On the one hand, some preliminary work of Dyk and Witkin (1965) analyzed the way parents encouraged their children to act independently. As a result children tended to be field-independent, but when children were encouraged to conform to authority, children inclined to be more field-dependent. In the same way, coping strategies with loneliness were different for teenagers according to style differences (J.C. Woodward & V. Kalyan-Masih, 1990). Specifically, the former study presented that FI adolescents engaged in individual pursuits, while FD resorted to religious, physical activity and professional help in order to cope with solitude. Furthermore, the study on English as a foreign language (EFL) incidental vocabulary acquisition, FD individuals had greater susceptibility to collaborative output task than FI ones (Q.Wang, 2019). Similarly, FI subjects performed a higher physical activity (PA) in organized sport in contrast to FD, who demonstrated less PA and weaker tendency to use body information in RFT respectively (Liu, W., & Chepyator-Thomson, J. R., 2009). To clarify, RFT measures the extent to which people can effectively use their body information (sense of verticality, vestibular and proprioceptive awareness, etc.). Hence, FI representatives are apt to competence in skills, enjoyment, involvement in PA and more significantly confidence in self (Graham, Holt/Hale & Parker, 2001). Thus, these findings have demonstrated FI-FD in light of behavioral style.

On the other hand, an increasing number of studies have found that FI-FD are differentiated on the basis of cognitive restructuring skills and disembedding ability being united into one spatial ability factor. For instance, Vernon (1972) revealed that FI measures did not define a factor distinct from spatial ability after conducting empirical study of the relationships between FI measures and tests of abilities. Similarly, after administering a battery of 9 tests to 81 undergraduates, Hyde, Geiringer, and Yen (1975) conducted a factor analysis which indicated that tests of spatial ability, field-independence, and mental arithmetic emerged together in a spatial ability factor. Another study on note-taking techniques (Frank, 1984) observed that FI had less wordy and arbitrary notes, while FD had wordier and less efficient notes showing the difference between

cognitive restructuring skills. Probably, this can be considered as one of the prerequisites to academic performance. More recent evidence (Zhang, 2004) has been supporting this perspective demonstrating the relationship between FDI and Geometry achievement where visual disembedding is relevant, but zero-order correlation with academic achievement among students with Chinese Language major and Mathematics. Another study highlights FI-FD has a direct effect on professional performance in simultaneous interpreting, where cognition is responsible for receiving, processing and producing information. (S. Ferdowsi & M. H. Razmi, 2022). On the basis of the above-mentioned findings it can be assumed that cognitive restructuring skills and disambiguation come into play and predict success in fields where those abilities are required. However, there is no recent study proving the direct relationship between CS and personality or broad behavioral dimension.

It is significant to consider that methodology has played a crucial role in these findings. Indeed, EFT, RFT, GEFT do measure visual, perceptual and spatial ability and bring it down to one factor. Procedural variables may also influence in a different way on some participants. This probably elucidates why females tend to obtain lower scores than males on measures of FI such as the RFT (Richardson, 1997). Finally, research methods where field-independent learners in one study might well represent the field-dependent learners in another study due to different methods employed by researchers to categorize their participants (Kozhevnikov, 2007).

Visual, perceptual or spatial ability are not considered in the context of Social Media Instagram in comparison to interpretation studies, note-taking techniques and proficiency in Geometry. Therefore, this study will go beyond cognition and try to explore FI-FD in the context of behavioral style concerning disembedding the outward feedback, references of beauty, success and lifestyle in general.

2.4 Social media Instagram influence

Social media is another type of reality, a virtual one resting on internet-based interactions. According to Carr and Hayes, 2015 social media has been enabling users to interact and manage online identity, either in real-time or async, with both broad and narrow audiences who get value from user-generated content and the perceived interactivity with others. In fact, emotions, thoughts, impressions and reactions can be presented via ever-updating likes, comments, reposts, reactions, tags and etc. In comparison to real-life interaction, the internet-based one has the advantages of greater control and freedom, destrained and asynchronous communication and accessibility to mass audiences (Carr & Hayes, 2015). As a result, mass media has been contributing to societal values and mass standards of beauty, success, body image, eating habits, etc (Levine & Harrison, 2009).

Fardouly, 2017 authority on the relationship between social media and appearance comparison, affirms that upward comparison on social media is most frequently made leading to poorer body image among college-age women. This finding can also be observed

in a review of 67 studies exploring the connection between Internet use and body as well as eating concerns (Rodgers & Melioli, 2016). Another study by Brooks, 2015 found that college students were upset when they relied on social media as a self-disclosure, receiving negative feedback. This is congruent with recent research on self-worth and social media feedback (Sabik, Falat & Magagnos, 2019). Specifically, female representatives who rely their worth on feedback illustrated lower resilience, self-kindness, higher levels of stress as well as depressive symptoms. Thus, when outward-Instagram becomes a standard, individuals are in danger to perceive perfectly managed online identity and one's lifestyle as a real or a pattern distorting the perception of self and life. However, Instagram also has a set of advantages. It gives access to communication with others online, decreasing depression and loneliness, rising self-esteem and social support (Shaw and Gant, 2004). In the same way, it probably can serve as a tool for inspiration and motivation.

As reported findings were presented, Instagram was not intended to perniciously impact the well-being of individual and it does not do so now, rather it is within the attitude of individual to choose to what extent to rely on external on internal referent while making judgements, forming considerations, assumptions and definitions of beauty, health behavior, happiness and success.

Chapter three: Methodology

3.1 Research design

This study uses the quantitative non-experimental research design involving test and self-administered survey to examine the relationship between variables in real life conditions (Cresswell, 2009, p. 27). The set of interviews were conducted to prepare the questions for the self-administered survey.

To understand the relationship between Social Network experience on Instagram, I considered participants' cognitive style measured via Embedded figure test (Gottschaldt, 1926). It is significant to mention, that EFT was employed since it is an objective measure of cognition including figures in contrast to the predetermined set of questions that can be subjectively answered within regular tests. The survey design on Social Network experience on Instagram aimed to observe how feedback and content (success, appearance, body image, achievement) influence participants, how users manage an online identity and what attitude towards self and the world they have. According to Mujis (2011), surveys are informative on individual's opinions, attitudes, experiences (p.30) via constructed questions that can be analyzed statistically. Similarly, cross-sectional methodological design in survey research was used because data was gathered from one sample and at one point in time.

3.2 Research site

The test and survey were conducted among employed young adults and undergraduate students studying at KAZGUU, ENU and Nazarbayev universities. The first one has 28 years of education experience allowing students to learn national law, economics, humanities and social sciences, the next has 26 years of education experience in engineering, economics and

humanities, while the third has 12 years of experience offering majors in medicine, humanities, engineering and digital, mining and geosciences. The participants who chose “others” are self-employed. The test and survey were proliferated via social media such as Instagram, Telegram and What’s Up.

The reason for selecting this site is availability as well as consent of students and approval from the University supervisor.

3.3 Sample

This study used a non-probability convenience sampling technique. A total of 44 participants were recruited. The sample was subdivided on the basis of interviewees and participants for quantitative analysis where 35 subjects were assessed. According to E.Sidorenko, the authority in quantitative analysis, the number of participants has to be $n \geq 30$ to do the statistical analysis. The mean age of young adults constitutes 21 accounting for 97,1 % female and 2,9% male. The major part comprises undergraduate students ranging from 1st to 4th year of study including majors in humanities, engineering, arts, mathematics and digital sciences. The selection criteria constituted location-Kazakhstan, age ranging from 18 to 24 and current usage of Social media Instagram. There were no special requirements concerning gender, ethnicity and economic background. Participants were invited to complete the online Google form survey and test at the onlinetestpad.com website (link was inserted within the form) being assured of full confidentiality and the use of the information specifically for scientific and academic purposes. To ensure anonymity, participants were recommended to use nicknames and use the ability to leave if they felt uncomfortable about the questions or research topic. In reference to interviews, all 9 interviewees signed the online informed consent beforehand. The full description at the beginning of the survey and test as well as informed consent was constructed according to APA ethics code principles and standards.

The rationale that pertains to such a choice of the selection criteria and sampling procedure include the fact that these individuals:

- are students and easy to be reached out.
- are in the age period characterizing sensitivity and vulnerability in relation to external influence.
- have Instagram account and are exposed to persistent content update and feedback from other users.

3.4 Research methods

To find whether there is a relationship between CS and Social Network Instagram experience, a cross-sectional test and self-administered survey among participants were used to derive the information. Also, the set of 9 interviews were organized to prepare components for the survey. Survey and test procedures were carried out one point in time by 7 female and 3 male respondents from 18 to 24 years old. I employed this design of the items for the reason of administering the variables. Embedded Figure Test and self-administered survey were approved by The Research and Ethics Committee, KAZGUU University.

3.5 Variables

The study test and self-administered survey included CS FI-FD and Social network Instagram experience categorical variables that were examined consequently in a proper manner as they were found to be correlated.

3.6 Measures

Interview. Participants were recruited via Whats’up. Interview protocol was approved by KAZGUU University supervisor prior to data collection. Participants were treated according to the APA ethics code principles and standards: they were provided online informed consent with full description of study (context, purpose, why the participant was chosen, time, procedure, benefit, potential risks, privacy, contact information) prior to the all data collection procedure.

There were 9 combined in-depth interviews with 9 participants involving both semi-structured and unstructured methods whilst the design implied the use of the later one. The exception was done for several reasons: the incomplete understanding of the research questions and the absence of experience conducting interviews. Thus, the process itself was educational, where researcher discovered new facets of interview organization.

The purpose of the interviews was to develop the questions for a final survey aiming to understand Social Network experience on Instagram.

The objectives:

- To check whether questions were unambiguous, not suggestive, answerable, interesting and consistent.
- To determine what questions interviewees perceived as sensitive and reformulate to a more ecological manner.
- To check what topics are mostly discussed during the interview to come up with new insightful questions.

The interview included 15 to 20 questions, where 4 ones were general, asking age, motivation, time spent and percentage representation of experience. The first questions allowed to build a rapport and dive into Instagram experience. There were raised topics in relation to appearance, body image, eating habits, life satisfaction wrapped into a unique user’s story. For example, how Instagram corroborated anxiety, how comparison devalued the image of body, face and how social media gave opportunity for interaction to them etc.

The study was carried out based on recommendations of the guidelines of research, Academic Quality Committee, KAZGUU University. The interview protocol and informed consent were approved by the supervisor.

Cognitive style. Online Embedded Figure Test (Gottschaldt, 1926) was used to measure cognitive style FI-FD. For each participant, the 30 item complex patterns with the options of 5 simple figures ranging from A to E were given. The aim of the test was to find out what simple figure suits for the offered complex pattern. The result was measured by dividing the number of correct answers onto the time spent in minutes. If the index is $\geq 2,5$ - the subject is FI; if the index is $\leq 2,5$ the

subject is FD. The results depended on the speed of test completion (M.A. Holodnaya, 2004).

Social network experience on Instagram. The self-administered online survey was used to understand what experience users derive. Each participant answered to 27 items from which 7 of them were aimed to get the background information (gender, date of birth, University, year of study, major, time spent on Instagram and motivation using uses and gratification theory) (Katz & Blumler, 1974), while the rest 20 items were aimed to understand how feedback and content influences subjects' perception of one's own success, appearance, body image, manner of managing of online identity, attitude towards self and the world. The answers were based on Likert Scale items with five points presented here:

- 1 Strongly agree
- 2 Agree
- 3 Neutral
- 4 Disagree
- 5 Strongly disagree

Figure 3. Likert scale

Both the self-administered survey and test were conducted in Russian language and translated to English, the language of study. All subjects received the Russian language instructions. The e-format of the survey was designed on the Google platform. The reliability of the instrument was verified by Cronbach alpha procedures in Excel. The 20 items of the survey demonstrated internal consistency with $\alpha=0,91$.

3.7 Limitations

1. The lack of motivation among students. Respondents did not participate in the online survey and test within five days after its distribution on social media (Instagram, What's up), email and offline attendance of the lectures with the permission of the professors from KAZGUU School of Liberal Arts. It turned out that difficulty was related with duration (approximately 30 minutes) of the test and survey. Therefore, I cut 6 questions in the survey during the data collection process and left 27 items.

2. Omission of the test part at the beginning. The test is a prerequisite to the survey as it measures CS of the participants, the independent variable of the study. Those who skipped the test I did not consider in quantitative analysis.

Chapter four: Data analysis

This section includes 3 stages: interview, survey and test, data analysis and description.

The first phase includes 9 interviews with 9 participants. It started after the interview protocol and informed consent were approved by the supervisor. During this process the questions were changed, becoming more clear, relevant and answerable for participants.

The second phase consists of the test and the survey. These instruments were employed after the consultations with the supervisor, faculty and approval of the Academic Quality Committee, KAZGUU University.

The third phase includes sample data, Cronbach alpha to evaluate the reliability of self-administered survey and chi-square test to observe the relationship between CS and Social Network experience on Instagram. All analyses were made in Excel google form.

The chi-square analysis was applied for several reasons listed here:

- Chi-square allows to work with non-metrical scales. The variables used in this study were nominal and ordinal (Nasledov, A. D. 2004).

- Chi-square allows to unite the small cells into one (Makarov, A. A, Pashkevich, A. V, Tambovceva, A. A. 2018). As the sample is not big enough, there were cells with 1 or 2 participants who were united into one cell. For example, the first question had 1 participant-strongly agree and 2 participants-agree, the former one was transferred to the later one.

- Chi-square was employed within past studies such as the relationship between CS and participation in organized sports (Graham, Holt/Hale & Parker, 2001).

To conduct the Chi-square test some statistical underpinnings were considered:

1. Alternative hypothesis and Null hypothesis

Ha: There is a relationship between Field-Independent-Field-Dependent cognitive style and Social Network experience on Instagram.

Ha: There is a relationship between Field-Independent and positive Social Network experience on Instagram.

Ha: There is a relationship between Field-Dependent and negative Social Network experience on Instagram.

H0: There is no relationship between Field-Independent-Field-Dependent cognitive style and Social Network experience on Instagram.

H0: There is no relationship between Field-Independent individuals and positive Social Network experience on Instagram.

H0: There is no relationship between Field-Dependent Individuals and negative Social Network experience on Instagram.

2. P -value $\leq 0,05$

3. *Degrees of freedom (df)*: $(rows-1)*(columns-1)$

4. If empirical value χ^2 is greater than critical value, reject H0.

Expected value: $fe' = fc * fr / N$

$\chi^2 = \sum (O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i$

Chapter five: Findings

Question 5: When I see the content representing a significantly greater lifestyle or success, I can hardly accept my life as per se. Chi-square Results.

Table 1

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 5</u>		
Labels	Cognitive style	
	<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree		
Agree	2,3	1,9
Neither agree nor disagree	0,05	0,04
Disagree	1,10	1,6
Strongly disagree	0,003	0,002
χ^2		7,9
<i>df</i>		3
<i>p-value</i>		0,05

Note. *df*-degrees of freedom

A significant relationship between CS and acceptance of one's own life was shown by the chi-square test, $\chi^2(3, N = 35) = 7.9, p \leq 0,05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating *df* (Hahn Fox, B., & Jennings, W. G., 2014). The alternative hypothesis was supported.

Question 6: I am inclined to devalue my achievements in contrast with successful users. Chi-square Results.

Table 2

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 6</u>		
Labels	Cognitive style	
	<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree	1,8	1,5
Agree	0,5	0,4
Neither agree nor disagree	0,04	0,03
Disagree	0,2	0,2
Strongly disagree	2,6	2,2
χ^2		9,5
<i>df</i>		4
<i>p-value</i>		0,05

A significant relationship between CS and attitude towards one's achievements was shown by the chi-square test, $\chi^2(4, N = 35) = 9.5, p \leq 0,05$.

Question 8: I can share a few examples where those standards of beauty led up to negative consequences. (ex: eating disorder). Chi-square Results. The alternative hypothesis was supported.

Table 3

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 8</u>		
Labels	Cognitive style	
	<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree	5,04	1,6
Agree	2,3	1,9
Neither agree nor disagree		
Disagree	1,1	0,9
Strongly disagree	0,7	0,6
χ^2		14,1
<i>df</i>		3
<i>p-value</i>		0,003

A significant relationship between CS and consequences prompted by beauty standards was shown by the chi-square test, $\chi^2(3, N = 35) = 14.1, p \leq 0,05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating *df*. The alternative hypothesis was supported.

Question 15: I am inclined to wear make-up when publishing photos/stories as a protection from the external world. Chi-square Results.

Table 4

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 15</u>		
Labels	Cognitive style	
	<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree		
Agree	0,003	0,9
Neither agree nor disagree	3,1	4,3
Disagree	0,9	0,8
Strongly disagree	0,5	0,4
χ^2		10,9
<i>df</i>		3
<i>p-value</i>		0,01

A significant relationship between CS and make-up usage as a protection was shown by the chi-square, $\chi^2(3, N = 35) = 10.9, p \leq 0,05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating *df*. The alternative hypothesis was supported.

Question 16: The more I use Instagram, the more I need instant gratification. (looking for updates in the feed). Chi-square Results.

Table 5

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 16</u>		
Labels	Cognitive style	
	<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree	2,6	2,2
Agree	0,02	0,02
Neither agree nor disagree	1,9	1,6
Disagree	1,8	1,5
Strongly disagree	0,4	0,4
χ^2		12,5
<i>df</i>		4
<i>p-value</i>		0,01

A significant relationship between CS and instant gratification was shown by the chi-square, $\chi^2(4, N = 35) = 12.5, p \leq 0,05$. The alternative hypothesis was supported.

Question 17: The more I use Instagram, the more I need to get positive feedback. (likes, comments, reactions). Chi-square Results.

Table 6

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 17</u>		
Labels	Cognitive style	
	<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree	2,3	1,9
Agree	2,6	2,2
Neither agree nor disagree	0,4	0,4
Disagree	3,9	3,3
Strongly disagree	4,6	3,8
χ^2		25,3
<i>df</i>		4
<i>p-value</i>		0,00004

A significant relationship between CS and the need to get positive feedback was shown by the chi-square, χ^2 (4, $N = 35$) = 25.3, $p \leq 0,05$. The alternative hypothesis was supported.

Question 18: For the last 6 months-1 year of using Instagram, I have become less sympathetic towards myself. Chi-square Results.

Table 7

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 18</u>		
Labels	Cognitive style	
	<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree		
Agree	1,9	1,6
Neither agree nor disagree	2,7	2,3
Disagree	0,4	0,4
Strongly disagree	0,02	0,02
χ^2		9,4
<i>df</i>		3
<i>p-value</i>		0,02

A significant relationship between CS and attitude towards self was shown by the chi-square, χ^2 (3, $N = 35$) = 9.4, $p \leq 0,05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating *df*. The alternative hypothesis was supported.

The following results of 13 components illustrated the null hypothesis and low level of significance.

Question 1: I feel less significant receiving a little amount of feedback (likes, comments, reactions) after posting photos, stories, reels. Chi-square test.

Table 8

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 1</u>		
Labels	Cognitive style	
	<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree		
Agree	0,1	0,1
Neither agree nor disagree	0,006	0,005
Disagree		
Strongly disagree	0,03	0,02
χ^2		0,2
<i>df</i>		2
<i>p-value</i>		0,9

A chi-square test showed no relationship and lower significance level between CS and attitude towards self in terms of significance, $\chi^2 (2, N = 35) = 0.2, p \leq 0.05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating *df*. The null hypothesis was supported.

Question 2: I feel that feedback controls my mood. Chi-square test.

Table 9

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 2</u>		
Labels	Cognitive style	
	<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree		
Agree	0,5	0,4
Neither agree nor disagree	0,5	0,5
Disagree	0,003	0,002
Strongly disagree	0,03	0,02
χ^2		1,1
<i>df</i>		3
<i>p-value</i>		0,6

A chi-square test showed no relationship and lower significance level between CS and feedback towards mood, $\chi^2 (3, N = 35) = 1.1, p \leq 0.05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating *df*. The null hypothesis was supported.

Question 3: I feel that feedback controls my self-esteem. Chi-square test.

Table 10

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 3</u>		
Labels	Cognitive style	
	<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree		
Agree	0,02	0,02
Neither agree nor disagree	0,1	0,1
Disagree	0,2	0,2
Strongly disagree	0,1	0,1
χ^2		0,7
<i>df</i>		3
<i>p-value</i>		0,0

A chi-square test showed no relationship and lower significance level between CS and feedback towards self-esteem, $\chi^2 (3, N = 35) = 0.7, p \leq 0.05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating *df*. The null hypothesis was supported.

Question 4: I feel incomplete when I see posts with an “ideal” lifestyle thinking that others have more interesting and fulfilling lives. Chi-square test.

Table 11

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 4</u>			
Labels	Cognitive style		
		<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree			
Agree		3,2	2,7
Neither agree nor disagree		0,2	0,2
Disagree		0,5	0,4
Strongly disagree		0,2	0,5
χ^2			7,5
<i>df</i>			3
<i>p-value</i>			0,1

A chi-square test showed no relationship and lower significance level between CS and sense of incompleteness, $\chi^2(3, N = 35) = 7.5, p \leq 0,05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating *df*. The null hypothesis was supported.

Question 7: Instagram sets the standards of beauty, preventing me from accepting my appearance per se. Chi-square test.

Table 12

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 7</u>			
Labels	Cognitive style		
		<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree		2,6	2,2
Agree		0,2	0,2
Neither agree nor disagree			
Disagree		0,03	0,1
Strongly disagree		0,4	0,3
χ^2			6,9
<i>df</i>			3
<i>p-value</i>			0,1

A chi-square test showed no relationship and lower significance level between CS and acceptance of one's own appearance, $\chi^2(3, N = 35) = 6.9, p \leq 0,05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating *df*. The null hypothesis was supported.

Question 9: When I see posts with well-shaped influencers, I become upset. Chi-square test.

Table 13

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 9</u>			
Labels	Cognitive style		
		<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree			
Agree		0,2	0,2
Neither agree nor disagree		0,9	0,7
Disagree		0,2	0,5
Strongly disagree		0,02	0,02
χ^2			2,4
<i>df</i>			3
<i>p-value</i>			0,5

A chi-square test showed no relationship and lower significance level between CS and attitude towards body image, $\chi^2(3, N = 35) = 2.4, p \leq 0,05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating *df*. The null hypothesis was supported.

Question 10: I am afraid that others will criticize my appearance without using any filters within photos/stories. Chi-square test.

Table 14

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 10</u>		
Labels	Cognitive style	
	<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree		
Agree	0,1	0,1
Neither agree nor disagree		
Disagree	0,4	0,3
Strongly disagree	0,1	0,1
χ^2		1,2
<i>df</i>		2
<i>p-value</i>		0,5

A chi-square test showed no relationship and lower significance level between CS and usage of filters, $\chi^2(2, N = 35) = 1.2, p \leq 0,05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating *df*. The null hypothesis was supported.

Question 11: I feel less attractive when I receive little amount of feedback. Chi-square test.

Table 15

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 11</u>		
Labels	Cognitive style	
	<i>FI</i>	<i>FD</i>
Strongly agree		
Agree	0,1	0,1
Neither agree nor disagree	0,01	0,01
Disagree	1,3	1,1
Strongly disagree	0,5	0,5
χ^2		3,6
<i>df</i>		3
<i>p-value</i>		0,3

A chi-square test showed no relationship and lower significance level between CS and feedback, $\chi^2(3, N = 35) = 3.6, p \leq 0,05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating *df*. The null hypothesis was supported.

Question 12: Instagram allows me to create and show an ideal “image” of me and lifestyle. Chi-square test.

Table 16

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 12</u>			
Labels	Cognitive style		FD
		FI	
Strongly agree			
Agree		0,2	0,2
Neither agree nor disagree		0,3	0,3
Disagree		1,2	0,10
Strongly disagree		2,3	1,9
χ^2			7,2
<i>df</i>			3
<i>p-value</i>			0,1

A chi-square test showed no relationship and lower significance level between CS and inclination to create an “image”, $\chi^2 (3, N = 35) = 7.2, p \leq 0.05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating *df*. The null hypothesis was supported.

Question 13: I am afraid that this image can be destroyed. Chi-square test.

Table 17

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 13</u>			
Labels	Cognitive style		FD
		FI	
Strongly agree		0,4	0,3
Agree			
Neither agree nor disagree		0,01	0,01
Disagree		0,8	0,7
Strongly disagree		0,1	0,1
χ^2			2,4
<i>df</i>			3
<i>p-value</i>			0,5

A chi-square test showed no relationship and lower significance level between CS and fear that created “image” can be destroyed, $\chi^2 (3, N = 35) = 2.4, p \leq 0.05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating *df*. The null hypothesis was supported.

Question 14: I am inclined to post photos/stories in special clothes as a protection from the external world. Chi-square test.

Table 18

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 14</u>			
Labels	Cognitive style		FD
		FI	
Strongly agree			
Agree		1,4	1,2
Neither agree nor disagree		1,9	1,6
Disagree		0,4	0,4
Strongly disagree		0,3	0,3
χ^2			7,5
<i>df</i>			3
<i>p-value</i>			0,1

A chi-square test showed no relationship and lower significance level between CS and wearing of certain clothes, $\chi^2(3, N = 35) = 7,5, p \leq 0,05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating df . The null hypothesis was supported.

Question 19: For the last 6 months-1 year of using Instagram, I became less optimistic towards the world. Chi-square test.

Table 19

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 19</u>		
Labels	Cognitive style	
	FI	FD
Strongly agree	0,6	0,5
Agree		
Neither agree nor disagree	2,3	1,9
Disagree	0,4	0,3
Strongly disagree	0,002	0,002
χ^2		6,1
df		3
p -value		0,1

A chi-square test showed no relationship and lower significance level between CS and optimism, $\chi^2(3, N = 35) = 6,1, p \leq 0,05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating df . The null hypothesis was supported.

Question 20: Instagram positively influences me and my life. Chi-square test.

Table 20

<u>The difference between observed and expected counts for question 20</u>		
Labels	Cognitive style	
	FI	FD
Strongly agree		
Agree	0,2	0,2
Neither agree nor disagree	0,2	0,2
Disagree	1,4	1,2
Strongly disagree	1,3	1,1
χ^2		5,7
df		3
p -value		0,1

A chi-square test showed no relationship and lower significance level between CS and influence on life, $\chi^2(3, N = 35) = 5,7, p \leq 0,05$. The empty cells were not considered calculating df . The null hypothesis was supported.

In the end, 7 items demonstrated the acceptance of alternative hypotheses, while 13 items showed the acceptance of null ones.

Chapter Six: Discussion

The results partially confirm the relationship between CS FI-FD and Social network Instagram experience, where field-independent individuals are able to successfully disembody their perception of self and own life from others with no need to use make-up as a protection and feedback as a self-disclosure. In the same

way, they are independent from the rising urge of instant gratification in contrast to field-dependent ones. Probably, it contributes young adults to be sympathetic towards self, accept, enjoy life as well as themselves per se and value any achievements which is overall healthy for psychological well-being. Therefore, FI individuals might derive more positive Instagram experience using all advantages of internet-based communication. These results highlight that CS FI-FD has a broad dimension, a behavioral style representing a person as a whole. This substantiates previous findings in the literature of coping strategies with loneliness where FI adolescents engaged in individual pursuits, while FD resorted to religious, physical activity and professional help in order to cope with solitude. (J.C. Woodward & V. Kalyan-Masih, 1990).

However, the major part of the findings are not consistent with alternative hypotheses. Curiously, similar items concerning impact of feedback on sense of significance, self-esteem and mood, appearance, body image, wearing of certain clothes for purpose and managing “perfect” online identity identified no substantial correlation and statistical significance for both FI and FD young adults. These findings corroborate the statement that CS FI-FD is a spatial ability factor responsible only for visual, spatial and perceptual disembedding ability and cognitive restructuring skills. Thus, it does not pertain to personality as a whole. This is in complete agreement with Vernon (1972) and Hyde, Geiringer, Yen (1975) studies highlighting that CS FI-FD represents spatial, perceptual and visual abilities.

Although the results demonstrated discordance with alternative hypotheses, the findings have attempted to partially answer the research question. Thus, cognitive style might have predictive power at Social Network experience on Instagram where FI derive more positive input in comparison to FD, but further investigation is required.

There are several limitations causes of possible misalignment. Specifically, the usage of one tool of statistical analysis, categorical mistake and a small sample size of 35 participants, where the major part is women. First of all, in a case of a small sample, FI-FD index strain after the middle, where any number speculation can show a different index. In contrast with a large and more representative sample of approximately 300 people, the allocation of index can be more extreme whether to FI or FD styles and correlation will be demonstrated in the other way. Secondly, it is recommended to include more than one tool for statistical analysis to compare the results. Lastly, the hypothesis does not imply the absolute assumption that the FI category is better than FD. As it was said previously, two ends are equally important in certain conditions. Therefore, this perspective is advised to be considered in the future studies.

Chapter Seven: General conclusions

This paper has investigated the relationship between CS FI-FD and Social Media Network experience on Instagram, partially supporting its relation. The study is provisional and a first attempt to demonstrate the holistic nature of human functioning and its relevance, significance on Social Media platform which has been pertaining into the life of individuals every day. In my opinion, with the use of large and representative sample size and various statistical tools we can get more reliable results and state final conclusions.

References

- Abrams, Z. (2022). Why young brains are especially vulnerable to social media. *American Psychological Association*. <https://www.apa.org/news/apa/2022/social-media-children-teens>
- Abrams, Z. (2022). How can we minimize Instagram’s harmful effects? *American Psychological Association*. 53(2),30. <https://www.apa.org/monitor/2022/03/feature-minimize-instagram-effects>
- Bertini, M., Pizzamiglio, L., Wapner, S., & Wapner, S. (2013). *Field Dependence in Psychological Theory, Research and Application: Two Symposia in Memory of Herman A. Witkin* (1st ed.). Routledge.
- Burnette, C. B., Kwitowski, M. A., & Mazzeo, S. E. (2017). “I don’t need people to tell me I’m pretty on social media.” A qualitative study of social media and body image in early adolescent girls. *Body Image*, 23, 114–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bodyim.2017.09.001>
- Carr, C. T., & Hayes, R. A. (2015). *Social Media: Defining, Developing, and Divining*. *Atlantic Journal of Communication*, 23(1), 46–65. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15456870.2015.972282>
- Caleb T. Carr & Rebecca A. Hayes (2015) *Social Media: Defining, Developing, and Divining*, *Atlantic Journal of Communication*, 23:1, 46-65, DOI: 10.1080/15456870.2015.972282
- Cohen, R., Newton-John, T., & Slater, A. (2018). ‘Selfie’-objectification: The role of selfies in self-objectification and disordered eating in young women. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 79, 68–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2017.10.027>
- Concordia University. (2020, March 4). Examples of cognitive restructuring. Examples of Cognitive Restructuring. Retrieved June 1, 2022, from <https://www.concordia.ca/cunews/offices/provost/health/topics/stress-management/cognitive-restructuring-examples.html#:~:text=Cognitive%20restructuring%20is%20a%20technique,that%20do%20not%20produce%20stress.>
- Colbert, C. Y., French, J. C., Arroliga, A. C., & Bierer, S. B. (2019). Best practice versus actual practice: an audit of survey pretesting practices reported in a sample of medical education journals. *Medical Education Online*, 24(1), 1673596. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10872981.2019.1673596>
- Creswell, J. (2009). *Education research: Planning, Conducting and evaluating Quantitative and qualitative research*. 4th ed. Harlow: Pearson education limited.
- Denney, A. S., & Tewksbury, R. (2013). How to Write a Literature Review. *Journal of Criminal Justice Education*, 24(2), 218–234. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10511253.2012.730617>
- Dyk, R. B., & Witkin, H. A. (1965). Family Experiences Related to the Development of Differentiation in Children. *Child Development*, 36(1), 21. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1126779>
- Evans, C., Richardson, J. T. E., & Waring, M. (2013). Field independence: Reviewing the evidence. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 83(2), 210–224. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjep.12015>
- Fotiadis, A., Abdulrahman, K., & Spyridou, A. (2019). The Mediating Roles of Psychological Autonomy, Competence and Relatedness on Work-Life Balance and Well-Being. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01267>
- Ferdowsi, S., Razmi, M.H. Examining Associations Among Emotional Intelligence, Creativity, Self-efficacy, and Simultaneous Interpreting Practice Through the Mediating Effect of Field Dependence/Independence: A Path Analysis Approach. *J Psycholinguist Res* 51, 255–272 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10936-022-09836-0>
- Frank, B. M. (1984). Effect of Field Independence-Dependence and Study Technique on Learning From a Lecture. *American Educational Research Journal*, 21(3), 669–678. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312021003669>

17. Goodenough, D. R. (1976). The role of individual differences in field dependence as a factor in learning and memory. *Psychological Bulletin*, 83(4), 675–694. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.83.4.675>
18. Hayes, J., & Allinson, C. W. (1998). Cognitive Style and the Theory and Practice of Individual and Collective Learning in Organizations. *Human Relations*, 51(7), 847–871.
19. Hahn Fox, B., & Jennings, W. G. (2014). How to Write a Methodology and Results Section for Empirical Research. *Journal of Criminal Justice Education*, 25(2), 137–156. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10511253.2014.888089>
20. Hoffman, D. L., & Novak, T. P. (2012). Why Do People Use Social Media? Empirical Findings and a New Theoretical Framework for Social Media Goal Pursuit. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1989586>
21. Hyde, J. S., Geiringer, E. R., & Yen, W. M. (1975). On the Empirical Relation Between Spatial Ability and Sex Differences in Other Aspects of Cognitive Performance. *Multivariate Behavioral Research*, 10(3), 289–309. doi:10.1207/s15327906mbr1003_3
22. Kozhevnikov, M. (2007). Cognitive styles in the context of modern psychology: Toward an integrated framework of cognitive style. *Psychological Bulletin*, 133(3), 464–48
23. Jones, N. A., H. Ross, T. Lynam, P. Perez, and A. Leitch. 2011. Mental models: an interdisciplinary synthesis of theory and methods. *Ecology and Society* 16(1): 46. URL: <http://www.ecologyandsociety.org/vol16/iss1/art46/1>. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.133.3.464>
24. Liu, W., & Chepyator-Thomson, J. R. (2009). Field dependence–independence and physical activity engagement among middle school students. *Physical Education & Sport Pedagogy*, 14(2), 125–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408980801974960>
25. Legault, L. (2016). The Need for Autonomy. *Encyclopedia of Personality and Individual Differences*, 1–3. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-28099-8_1120-1
26. Muijs, D. (2010). *Doing Quantitative Research in Education with SPSS* (2nd ed.). SAGE Publications Ltd.
27. Morris, T. L., & Bergum, B. O. (1978). A note on the relationship between field-independence and creativity. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 46(3, Pt 2), 1114. <https://doi.org/10.2466/pms.1978.46.3c.1114>
28. Sabik, N.J., Falat, J. & Magagnos, J. When Self-Worth Depends on Social Media Feedback: Associations with Psychological Well-Being. *Sex Roles* 82, 411–421 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-019-01062-8>
29. Tinajero, C., & Páramo, M. F. (1997). Field dependence-independence and academic achievement: a re-examination of their relationship. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 67(2), 199–212. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8279.1997.tb01237.x>
30. Vernon, P. E. (1972). The distinctiveness of field independence. *Journal of Personality*, 40(3), 366–391. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.1972.tb00068.x>
31. Wang, Q. (2019). EFL Incidental Vocabulary Acquisition and Retention: Effects of Different Collaborative Output Tasks on Field Independent/Dependent Learners. *The Journal of AsiaTEFL*, 16(4), 1201–1218. <https://doi.org/10.18823/asiatefl.2019.16.4.9.1201>
32. Whiting, A., & Williams, D. (2013). Why people use social media: a uses and gratifications approach. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 16(4), 362–369. <https://doi.org/10.1108/qmr-06-2013-0041>
33. Witkin, H. A., & Goodenough, D. R. (1977). Field dependence and interpersonal behavior. *Psychological Bulletin*, 84(4), 661–689. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.84.4.661>
34. Woodward, John C & Kalyan-Masih, Violet.(1990). Loneliness, Coping Strategies and Cognitive Styles of the Gifted Rural Adolescent. *Adolescence; Roslyn Heights*, 25 (100), 977-88.
35. Zhang, L. F. (2004). Field-dependence/independence: cognitive style or perceptual ability?—validating against thinking styles and academic achievement. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 37(6), 1295–1311. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2003.12.015>
36. Cambridge Dictionary. (2022, May 25). referent definition: 1. the person, thing, or idea that a word, phrase, or object refers to: 2. the person, thing, or. . . Learn more. [Dictionary.Cambridge.Org. https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/referent](https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/referent)
37. Cambridge Dictionary. (2022a, May 25). interaction definition: 1. an occasion when two or more people or things communicate with or react to each other: 2. an. . . Learn more. [Dictionary.Cambridge.Org. https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/interaction](https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/interaction)
38. Collectivism | sociology. (2022). *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/collectivism>
39. Crocker, J., & Wolfe, C. T. (2001). Contingencies of self-worth. *Psychological Review*, 108(3), 593–623. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295x.108.3.593>
40. Online Test Pad. (2011–2022). Embedded Figure Test. Russian version. <https://onlinetestpad.com/ru/test/13935-test-vklyuchennykh-figur>
41. NapoleonCat. (2022, March 1). Instagram users in Kazakhstan - March 2022. <https://napoleoncat.com/stats/instagram-users-in-kazakhstan/2022/03/>
42. Наследов, А. Д. (2004). Математические методы психологического исследования. Издательство “Речь”.
43. Сидоренко, Е. В. (2000). Методы математической обработки в психологии. Издательство “Речь”.
44. Макаров, А. А, Пашкевич, А. В, Тамбовцева, А. А. (2018). *Задачник по математической статистике для студентов социально-гуманитарных и управленческих специальностей*. Издательство МЦНМО
45. The link to the test and survey: <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1mW3wRFqDgDVW9kw6pJaktYk1Nhn2sD6cPPGrGiFW2DE/edit?usp=sharing>